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THE APENNINE SIBYL

A MYSTERY AND A LEGEND

THE APENNINE SIBYL: A JOURNEY INTO HISTORY IN SEARCH OF THE ORACLE¹

1. Back to the fifteenth century and beyond

In the fifteenth century a strange rumour began to circulate throughout Europe, that a magical place was to be found in a remote mountain of central Italy, far from the main routes which led pilgrims and wayfarers from the European regions in the north to the holy center of Christianity and former capital city of a long-gone empire, Rome.

Tales started to be told about a Sibyl, who had her abode beneath a peak in the Apennine range, between the Italian provinces of Umbria and Marche: her cave, whose entrance was right on the mountain-top, was the access to a sort of enchanted realm, well buried under the rocky bulk of the mount, inhabited by gorgeous damsels and provided with all the bounties a human heart could ever wish for. The Sibyl, an oracle and a prophetess, presided over all that, foretelling things to come and luring the visiting knights into sin, until their soul was lost forever to evil and damnation.

This legendary narration experienced a widespread diffusion following the successful release of a romance, *Guerrino the Wretch* by the Italian storyteller Andrea da Barberino, and a travel account, *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl*, written by Antoine de la Sale, a French gentleman: they both reported about the sinister lore according to which a Sibyl was living under a mountain raising between Norcia and Montemonaco. A lore that would attract people from all over Europe, for many centuries, to the solitary,

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crowned peak of Mount Sibyl, where a gloomy cavern waited for visitors to enter its bowels and meet their own doom.

Fig. 1 - Mount Sibyl, a peak raising in the Italian Apennines between the provinces of Umbria and Marche

All that took place during the fifteenth century.

The question is: what had happened before that time?

If we want to cast a probing light on the thorny issue concerning the mysterious, enigmatic origin of the legend of the Apennine Sibyl, we need to understand whether the legendary tale about that Sibyl was already extant, and attested, in previous centuries. Was the Sibyl already known and referenced to before the fifteenth century? Can we retrieve any other mention of the Apennine Sibyl in works written in earlier centuries than *Guerrino the Wretch* and *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl*? Who else, if any - apart from Andrea da Barberino and Antoine de la Sale - ever wrote about the oracle who was thought to reside under an out-of-the-way mountain in central Italy?

When did the Sibyl actually start to dwell beneath that mount?

With the series of paragraphs that follows, we will try to explore this fascinating matter in depth. And we will find out that the answers we will be able to retrieve - or, the absence thereof - will tell us more than we expect on the true origin of the legendary tale of the Apennine Sibyl.

2. The earliest literary mentions of a Sibyl between Norcia and Montemonaco

When did it happen that a Sybil began to be regarded as living inside Mount Sibyl?

From the fifteenth century onwards, a legendary tale has spread across Europe, with a vitality that has endured for many hundreds of years: the myth of an Apennine Sibyl, with her subterranean realm concealed beneath a mountain that raises its crowned peak in a remote area of central Italy.

Fig. 2 - A closer view of Mount Sibyl's crowned top

The fame of the mythical tale was boosted by two literary works, both written in the fifteenth century: *Guerrino the Wretch*, a chivalric romance by Andrea da Barberino, a most successful best-seller for many centuries to come; and *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl*, an account of a visit that a French gentleman, Antoine de la Sale, made to the Sibyl's cliff and cave in 1420.

From then on, the renown of the cavern providing an entryway to a hidden sensual kingdom began its long-lasting journey throughout the European countries, gaining further strength owing to the identification of the Italian site with the legendary 'Mount Venus', a mythical peak that was depicted in an ancient German tale, which narrated of a knight whose name was Tannhäuser.

What did the two listed authors write in their respective works about the Apennine Sibyl?

In his *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl*, Antoine de la Sale, the French courtier, recounts «the wonders that are inside the mount of the Sibyl and by her lake [... the] Mount of Queen Sibyl of which I have heard many different talks» [In the original French text: «les merueilleuses choses qui sont es montz de la Sibille et de son lac [... le] mont de la royne Sibille, de quoy j'ay oui tant deviser en plusieurs manieres»].

Fig. 3 - The excerpt on the *Paradise of Queen Sibyl* as it appears in Antoine de la Sale's *La Salade*, a printed edition published in Paris in 1527

When it comes to Andrea da Barberino, in his chivalric romance *Guerrino the Wretch*, written in the first decades of the fifteenth century, he writes that «the mountains where the Sibyl is found are in the middle of Italy, where strong winds blow, for there the mounts are high and there lies the abode of griffins [...] so he went across the mountains of Aspromonte and travelled to the town of Norcia, which is in the midst of the great mountain of Apennine [...] And an elderly man, who had been listening to their words, replied to him: "Sir, he said the truth, that a Sibyl actually dwells beneath our mountainous fastnesses, for I remember that three young men came to this land: they went there, two of them came back and the other never returned"».

[In the original Italian text: «le montagne dove è la Sibilla è in mezo de Italia dove sono tuti venti per ché sono alte e za li stavano li grifoni; e la più pressa cità che li sia se chiama Norza [...] e passò le montagne de Asperamonte e vene a la cità de Norza la qual è in mezo de la grande montagna d'pinino [...] Respose uno homo anticho che se fermò audire parlare e disse o gentilhomo lo è vero quello che dice costui e che la Sibilla è in questa nostra montagna per ché io me ricordo venire tre gioveni in questa terra: che ando[ro]no li, doi tornono e l'altro non tornò mai»].

Fig. 4 - The passage on the mountains where the Sibyl has her abode in Andrea da Barberino's *Guerrino the Wretch*, as taken from an edition printed in Venice in 1480

So, in the early fifteenth century a Sibyl is already deeply nested into her subterranean realm set beneath a mountain in the vicinity of Norcia, not far from the small hamlet of Montemonaco.

But what about earlier centuries? If the legend that we call 'of the Apennine Sibyl' was truly originated in the region of the Sibillini Mountain Range, we should be able to find earlier mentions of that legend in previous literary works, belonging to medieval and even Roman times.

However, we find absolutely nothing. The Apennine Sibyl seems to have appeared there from sheer nonexistence, because no earlier documents ever mention her at all.

As a matter of fact, we will see that we cannot retrieve the slightest reference to a Sibyl living in the area of Norcia before the fifteenth century.

Is that true? Let's search and see.

3. The lack of medieval references to a Sibyl in the area of Norcia

In the fifteenth century, through the references contained in two literary works written by Andrea da Barberino and Antoine de la Sale, a Sibyl makes her appearance in a mountainous region of the Apennines in central Italy.

Where does she come from?

If we look for earlier mentions, we only encounter a perplexing void.

The oldest quote we know about the legends which are present in the area that we know today under the name of Sibillini Mountain Range is found in Petrus Berchorius, a benedictine abbot who writes in the first decades of the fourteenth century. As we reported in previous articles, in his *Reductorium Morale* Berchorius writes that «I heard a remarkable, horrific tale about Norcia, the Italian town... amid the peaks which raise near that town there is a lake, which from antique times is sacred to demons and conspicuously inhabited by them» [in the original Latin text: «Exemplum

terribile esse circa Norciam Italie civitatem audivi... inter montes isti civitati proximos esse lacum ab antiquis daemonibus consecratum et ab ipsis sensibiliter inhabitatum»].

Fig. 5 - Petrus Berchorius' *Reductorium Morale* and the excerpt on the lake of Norcia (Bibliothèque Nationale de France, Département des Manuscrits, Latin 16786)

Although Berchorius does mention a magical lake which we know today as the 'Lakes of Pilatus', he does not provide the least reference to any Sibyl living in any mountain raising in the same area.

And the same happens with Fazio degli Uberti, a poet born in Pisa in 1305, who mentions both Norcia and the Italian province of Marches in his poem *Dittamondo*: however, he only writes that «I don't want to overlook the renown of the Mount of Pilatus, where a lake is... to which, as described in Simon the Sorcerer, people ascend to consecrate their spellbooks - according to what local people say» [in the original Italian text: «la fama qui non vo' rimagna nuda - del monte di pillato, dov'è il lago [...] però che qua s'intende in Simon mago - per sagrar il suo libro in su monta - secondo che per quei di là si conta»].

Just like Berchorius, Fazio degli Uberti does not provide any reference to a Sibyl in the vicinity of Norcia. He writes his poem in the early second half of the fourteenth century.

Fig. 6 - The opening folium of Fazio degli Uberti's *Dittamondo* in a manuscript dating to 1447 (Bibliothèque Nationale de France, Département des Manuscrits, Italien 81)

Petrus Berchorius and Fazio degli Uberti are the only authors providing mentions of the legends active in the highlands of the Sibillini Mountain Range before Andrea da Barberino and Antoine de la Sale wrote their respective literary works. And the listed earlier authors do not utter a single word about a Sibyl, as they only report about the magical Lakes of Pilatus.

io uia scarioto onde tu uia
 secon dol dir dalcun da cui fui conto.
 La fama qui non uo rimagna nuda
 del monte di pillato doue illago
 che si guarda lestate amuda a muda.^{da}
 Pero che qua sintende in simon mago
 per sagrar il suo libro uui su monta
 onde tempesta poi con grande smago
 Secondo che per quei di la si conta.
 Canto .ij. tracta dela marcha dancona. r.

Fig. 7 - Fazio degli Uberti's verses on the Lake of Pilatus drawn from his *Dittamondo* (Bibliothèque Nationale de France, Département des Manuscrits, Italien 81, folium 95v)

Perhaps we may find references to an Apennine Sibyl living in the mountains surrounding Norcia in the ancient local historical sources. However, if we refer to the *Charters of the Municipality and People of the Land of Norcia* (*Statuti del Comune et Populo della Terra di Norcia*), a collection of laws and rules dating back to 1346 and published in a printed version in 1526, we don't find any reference to an Apennine Sibyl either. Book VI of the *Charters* is entirely devoted to the partition, for rural and livestock raising purposes, of the grasslands and highlands sitting at the foot of Mount Vettore, in the area where the small hamlet of Casteluccio di Norcia is set. But nothing is said about a Sibyl, in this Book and throughout the whole *Charters*.

Fig. 8 - The lion representing the town of Norcia in the printed edition of the *Statuti del Comune et Populo della Terra di Norcia*, 1526

Fig. 9 - The section dedicated to the partition of the highlands in the *Statuti del Comune et Popolo della Terra di Norcia*, 1526

Can we find any other reference to a Sibyl in Norcia's local history? Not much. For instance, we find an extensive text on the Sibyl's cave and the lakes of Pilatus in the *Chronicles of the antique town of Norsia*, a work written by Father Fortunato Ciucci, a monk of the order established by Pope Celestine V, part of the larger Benedictine monastic family. But it dates to 1653, a year which is very far from the fourteenth-century sources we would be glad to retrieve. And the same applies to a number of other local sources, such as seventeenth-century poet Giovan Battista Lalli, a native of Norcia who wrote many lines about the Sibyl.

If we turn to the eight books of the *Historical Chronicles of Norcia (Memorie Storiche di Norcia)*, written in 1869 by local scholar Feliciano Patrizi-Forti, a well-informed work on the history of the town from pre-Roman times up to the nineteenth century, a limited, almost negligible mention about the Apennine Sibyl is contained in Book VII, Chapter XIX, in the form of a short quote extracted from a report written by an emissary of the Pope, Innocenzo Malvasia, in 1587:

«At the shoulders of the said Mount [Castelluccio] eastward two lakes are found, which are described by Friar Leandro and more in depth by Biondo as to the relevant superstition; and four miles from them there is the Cave, which is said to belong to the Sibyl; of such cave and lakes many tales are

told, and a number of strange stories» [in the original Italian text: «A la spalla di detto Monte verso levante vi sono due laghi, de quali parla fra Leandro et più minutamente il Biondo, massime intorno alle superstizioni, et lontano di là circa quattro miglia vi è la Grotta, la qual dicono fusse de la Sibilla; de la qual grotta et laghi si raccontano molte cose, et varij accidenti»].

However, Innocenzo Malvasia writes in the sixteenth century, and he is just quoting from earlier passages drawn from the *Descrittione di tutta Italia* by Leandro Alberti, a work written in the first half of the same sixteenth century, and *De Italia Illustrata* by Flavio Biondo, written after 1440: both are late excerpts, adding nothing to our search for older quotes.

So we may turn to another intriguing reference provided by Feliciano Patrizi-Forti in Book 3, Chapter XXII, in which he makes reference to Castelluccio: there he adds a footnote containing a quote allegedly taken from the classical Greco-Roman geographer Claudius Ptolemy, which states that «in the Apennines there is a huge and frightful cavern which people calls the Sibyl's cave...» [«in Appennino immane horribileque antrum quod Sybillae caverna vulgo dicitur...» in the Latin footnote]. But - as we will see later in this article - even though this excerpt might seem to provide the 'smoking gun' as to the classical origin of the Apennine Sibyl, something is wrong in that. We will soon discuss it in full.

Only two quotes, a minor one and a footnote: at all appearances, Patrizi-Forti does not seem to consider the Sibyl's legend of any significance for Norcia or its history, with no mention of the Sibyl in the first books of his historical work, where he deals with Norcia's earlier and most antique history.

Thus, it largely appears to us that no early reference to an Apennine Sibyl is contained in any known local sources contained in the local historical archives of Norcia. The Sibyl just pops up in town from nothing with the mentions contained in *Guerrino the Wretch* by Andrea da Barberino and *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl* by Antoine de la Sale.

No presence of a Sibyl in the region of Norcia can be found before the beginning of the fifteenth-century backwards. No medieval text reports anything about an Apennine Sibyl.

May we find any reference in even earlier literary works? Do ancient Roman texts provide any mention of an Apennine Sibyl living in the mountains which lie between Norcia and Montemonaco? Was that Sibyl known in antiquity?

We will analyse this issue in detail in the next paragraph.

4. Ancient Rome, Lactantius and an enumeration of Sibyls

As we have seen in a previous article, no reference to an Apennine Sibyl can be found before the beginning of the fifteenth century. No medieval literary work mentions it at all, nor any evidence of her presence having been noticed and registered can be retrieved in the late-medieval *Charters* of the Municipality of Norcia.

So let's try and investigate further by going back to more antique times. Let's go back to ancient Rome, in search of a mention that may fully show that an Apennine Sibyl was known and recognised as living in the Apennines between Norcia and Montemonaco.

However, this is hard task either.

If we take into consideration the most renowned list of classical Sibyls provided in Book I, Chapter VI of the *De divinis institutionibus adversus gentes* by Lucius Caecilius Firmianus Lactantius, a Christian author and advisor to Emperor Constantine the Great in the fourth century, we find that in Lactantius' enumeration of ten Sibyls there is nothing that may possibly refer to our inhabitant of the Apennines:

«It is known that Sibyls were ten in number. Marcus Varro enumerated them all under the writers, who wrote an account of each. The first was from the Persians, and of her Nicanor made mention, who wrote the deeds of Alexander of Macedon. The second was of Libya, and of her Euripides made mention in the prologue of the Lamia. The third of Delphi, concerning whom Chrysippus speaks in that book which he composed concerning divination. The fourth a Cuma in Italy, whom Naevius

mentions in his books about the Punic war, and Piso in his annals. The fifth of Erythraea, whom Apollodorus of Erythraea affirms to have been his own country-woman. She foretold to the Greeks when they were setting off for Ilium, both that Troy was doomed to destruction, and that Homer would write lies...».

Fig. 10 - The table of content in a most valuable edition of Lucius Caecilius Firmianus Lactantius' *De Divinis Institutionibus*, printed in 1465 at the benedictine abbey of Subiaco (Italy)

[In the original Latin text: «Ceterum Sibillas decem numero fuisse. Easque omnes [M. Varro] numeravit sub auctoribus, qui de singulis scriptitarunt. Primam fuisse de Persis, cujus mentionem fecerit Nicanor, qui res gestas Alexandri Macedonis scripsit. Secundam Libicam cujus meminit Euripides in Lamiae prologo. Tertiam Delphicam de qua Chrisippus loquitur in eo libro quem de divinatione composuit. Quartam Cumaeam in Italia, quam Nevius in libris belli Punici, Piso in annalibus nominant. Quintam Erithraeam, quam Appollodorus erithraeus affirmat suam fuisse civem. Eamque Graiis Ilium petentibus vaticinatam et perituram esse Trojam et Homerum mendatia scripturum»].

In this first passage taken from Lactantius' enumeration - quoting in turn from a lost excerpt from "Antiquitates rerum humanarum et divinarum", a lost work written by Marcus Terentius Varro, a first century B.C. scholar - including the first five Sibyls, no oracle shows any relationship with the Apennines in Italy. Even the fourth Sibyl, the «Cumaean», sometimes referred to as the «Cimmerian», has no links with the Apennines, as she is

strongly connected to the area of Cumae, near Naples, and the Cumaean Sibyl, listed under no. 7 within the catalogue set down by Lactantius, as noted by many scholars and was fully demonstrated in my previous article “A Sibyl called Cimmerian: exploring the potential link to the Apennine Sibyl”.

But let's proceed with the enumeration provided by Lactantius:

«Sixth of Samos, respecting whom Eratosthenes writes that he had found a written notice in the ancient annals of the Samians. The seventh was of Cumae, by name Amalthea, who is termed by some Demophile and they say that she brought nine books to the king Tarquinius Priscus [...] The eighth was from the Hellespont, born in the territory of Troy, in the village of Marpeesus, about the town of Gergithus; and Heraclides of Pontus writes that she lived in the times of Solon and Cyrus. The ninth of Phrygia, who gave oracles at Ancyra. The tenth of Tibur, by name Albunea, who is worshipped at Tibur as a goddess, near the banks of the river Anio, in the depths of which her statue is said to have been found, holding in her hand a book».

[In the original Latin text: «Sextam Samiam de qua scripsit Eratosthenes in antiquis annalibus Samiorum repperisse se scriptum. Septimam Cumanam nomine Amaltheam quae ab aliis Demophile nominatur, eamque novem libros attulisse ad regem Tarquinium Priscum [...]. Octavam Hellespontiaca in agro troiano natam vico marmesso circa oppidum gergithium quam scribit Heraclides Ponticus Solonis et Cyri fuisse temporibus. Nonam Phrygiam, quae vaticinata sit Ancile. Decimam Tiburtem nomine Albuneam quae Tiburi colitur ut dea juxta ripas amnis Anienis, cujus in gurgite simulacrum ejus inventum esse dicitur tenens in manu librum»].

In this second part of the enumeration, no reference to an Apennine Sibyl is found either, being the only Italian Sibyls mentioned by Lactantius the most famous ones from Cumae (near Naples) and Tibur (Tivoli near Rome).

So the list of ancient Sibyls belonging to the classical world provided by Lactantius does not offer any hint in favour of a potential ancient origin of an oracular site set amid the Apennines.

rous multiplicat: uel ab unius cuius nomine uel a consiliis deoꝝ denun-
 tiandis eius deos non appellabant eolico genere sermonis. Ceteroꝝ sibillas decē
 numero fuisse: easq; oēs numero fuisse. Easq; oēs numerauit sub auctoribus
 q; de singulis scripitarūt. Primā fuisse de persis cuius mentionē fecit Nica-
 nor qui res gestas Alexandri macedonis scripsit. Secundam libicam cuius
 meminit Euripides in Iamie plogo. Tertiā delphicam de qua Chrisippus
 loquit in eo libro quē de diuinatione composuit. Quartam Cumeā in Italia:
 quā nemius in libris belli punici: piso in annalibus noiet. Quintā erichreā:
 quā appollodorus erichreus affirmat suam fuisse ciuem. Eamq; gratis ilium
 petentibus uaticinata et periturā esse troiam et homerū mendacia scriptu-
 rum. Sextam samiam de qua scripsit erathostenes in antiquis analibus samioꝝ
 repperisse se scriptū. Septimā cumanaē noie amaltheam que ab aliis demo-
 phyle noiaē. eamq; nouē libros attulisse ad regem Tarquiniū priscū ac p
 eis trecentos philippos postulasse: regēq; aspernatū pretii magnitudinem:
 mulieris insaniam: illam in conspectu regis tres combussisse: ac p reliquis
 idem pretiū postulasse. Tarquiniū multo magis mulierē insanire putasse:
 que denuo tribus aliis exultis: quom in eodem pretio pseueraret: motū esse
 regem: ac residuos trecentis aureis emisse: quoz; postea numerus sic actus:
 capitolio refecto quod ex omnibus ciuitatibus & italicis & grecis & pre-
 cipue erichreis coacti allatiq; sunt romam: cuiuscumq; sibilē noie fuerunt.
 Octauā hellepontiacā in agro troiano natam nico marmesso circa oppidū
 gurgithiū quā scribit heraclides ponticus Solonis & Cyri fuisse tēporibus.
 Nonam phrygiā: que uaticinata sit ancile. Decimā tiburtem noie albuneā
 que tiburini colit ut dea iuxta ripas amnis anienis: cuius in gurgite sumula-
 chru eius iuenuū esse dicit. tenens in manu librum. Harū omium sibillarum

Fig. 11 - The enumeration of Sibyls from the 1465 edition of Lucius Caecilius Firmianus Lactantius' *De Divinis Institutionibus*

Can we tread any other ancient trail in search of a confirmation - if any - of the presence of an Apennine Sibyl when Rome was a prominent power in the antique world? Let's analyse a number of other mentions and see whether they are relevant.

5. Oracular and devotional sites in the Apennines

In our journey through the history of ancient Rome in search of a possible classical origin for the legend of the Apennine Sibyl, we have highlighted

the lack of a mention in the well-known enumeration provided by Lucius Caecilius Firmianus Lactantius in the fourth century A.D.

However, undeniably Roman literature actually registers some sort of connection between prophesying oracles and the Apennine Mountain Range, the rocky chain which runs throughout the entire spine of the Italian peninsula.

So let's review the known excerpts which mention such a specific connection (oracular sites and the Apennines) to ascertain whether they feature any link with the Apennine Sibyl's legend and lore. We already presented those excerpts in our previous article *World of the Sibyl: the Italian Apennines and the Sibillini Mountain Range*, and we briefly review them again here.

An interesting passage is contained in the *Historia Augusta*, a collection of biographies of Roman emperors written in the fourth century. In the section dedicated to Claudius II Gothicus, who was proclaimed Emperor by his legions in 268 A.D, we find a potential connection to oracles and the Italian Apennines.

Fig. 12 - The section on Claudius II Gothicus from the *Historia Augusta* (Vatican Apostolic Library, manuscript Pal. Lat. 899, ninth century)

After having asked an oracular response about the fortunes of his lineage in Comagena, a Roman outpost at the frontier with the Noricum (Danube region), Emperor Claudius moves to another oracle set in the Italian Apennines, as Latin author Trebellio Pollio reports:

«Similarly, when, once in the Apennines, he asked about his own future, he received the following reply: "Three times only shall summer behold him a ruler in Latium". Likewise, when he asked about his descendants: "Neither a goal nor a limit will I set for their power". Again, when he asked about his brother Quintillus, whom he was planning to make his associate in the imperial power, the reply was: "Fate shall display him to people on earth not for long"».

[In the original Latin text: «Item cum in Appennino de se consuleret, responsum huius modi accepit: "Tertia dum latio regnantem viderit aestas". Item cum de posteris suis: "His ego nec metas rerum nec tempora ponam". Item cum de fratre Quintillo, quem consortem habere volebat imperii, responsum est: "Ostendent terris hunc tantum fata"»].

Fig. 13 - The excerpt from the Historia Augusta mentioning an oracle in the Apennines (Vatican Apostolic Library, manuscript Pal. Lat. 899, ninth century)

Therefore, we have an oracle who delivers his/her prophecies amid the rugged peaks of the Apennines, a first hint to a special, magical character featured by Italy's mountainous backbone. However, the text provides no further clues as to where this oracular site is situated. Nor the specific presence of a Sibyl is mentioned.

A further relevant quote is taken from the celebrated work *The Twelve Caesars* by first-century Latin writer Gaius Suetonius Tranquillus. In the passages dedicated to Aulus Vitellius Germanicus Augustus, who reigned as an Emperor in 69 A.D. for nine months, after the short-lived Galba and Otho, we find an account of a special night of revelling and celebration that Vitellius held in the Apennines following the defeat and death of his rival-Emperor Otho:

«He openly drained a great draught of unmixed wine and distributed some among the troops. With equal bad taste and arrogance, gazing upon the stone inscribed to the memory of Otho, he declared that he deserved such a Mausoleum, and sent the dagger with which his rival had killed himself to the Colony of Agrippina, to be dedicated to Mars. He also held a ritual vigil throughout the night on the heights of the Apennines. Finally he entered the city (Rome) to the sound of the trumpet, wearing a general's mantle and a sword at his side...».

[In the original Latin text: «plurimum meri propalam hausit passimque divisit. Pari vanitate atque insolentia lapidem memoriae Othonis inscriptum intuens, dignum eo Mausoleo ait, pugionemque, quo is se occiderat, in Agrippinensem coloniam misit Marti dedicandum. In Appennini quidem iugis etiam pervigilium egit. Urbem denique ad classicum introiit paludatus ferroque succinctus...»].

According to Suetonius, Aulus Vitellius left Gaul and - in his course to Rome to be acclaimed as the new victorious Emperor - he stopped one full night with his troops amid the Apennines, his ancestral homeland (his family was of Sabine origin, «stirpem ex Sabinis»), for a sacred festival, a sort of thanksgiving to the divine favor. But which mount or valley did Aulus Vitellius exactly select to carry out his vigil? Nobody knows. But sure enough the Apennines had a special attractiveness for oracles, shrines and devotional practices, even though Suetonius makes no reference to any Sibyl.

Fig. 14 - The section on Emperor Vitellius in Suetonius' *The Twelve Caesars* (Bibliothèque Nationale de France in Paris, Département des Manuscrits, Lat 6115, ninth century)

Fig. 15 - The Apennines as mentioned in Suetonius' *The Twelve Caesars*

So, we still are not able to find any evidence that an Apennine Sibyl, set between Norcia and Montemonaco, was known and addressed by querying visitors in Roman times.

However, it is easily perceived that the Apennines were considered as a place where oracles and prophecies were given. And we also know for certain that a Sibyl actually rendered her oracular responses amid the elevations of the Apennines. Who was she? Unfortunately, she was not the Apennine Sibyl we are looking for: instead, she was another old acquaintance of ours, the tenth Sibyl listed in the classical enumeration provided by Lactantius.

She just was the Tiburtine Sibyl. As we will detail in the next paragraph.

6. A Sibyl in the Apennines (the Tiburtine)

In our previous article, we saw that Romans considered the Apennines as a fitting place to render oracular prophecies and hold special devotional celebrations. However, we have found no reference to the possible presence of a Sibyl in the Apennines, and namely of an Apennine Sibyl in the area of today's Sibillini Mountain Range.

Yet, according to an antique tradition, a Sibyl was actually referenced as active in the Apennines. Was that the Apennine Sibyl? No: it was the Tiburtine Sibyl, the tenth Sibyl listed in Lactantius' catalogue, and also known as 'Albunea'.

Fig. 16 - The Tiburtine Sibyl in a fresco at the Cappella della Madonna Immacolata in Padua (Italy)

But wasn't the Tiburtine Sibyl located at Tibur, or modern Tivoli, a small town sitting just some fifteen miles east of Rome?

Yes. Nonetheless, we must consider that Tivoli is located on the first elevations of the Tiburtine Mountains, part of the greater chain of the Apennines: a picturesque setting, with waterfalls and ravines - today as it was in past millennia. And the Tiburtine Mountains were actually considered, in antiquity, as rugged, elevated peaks.

In fact, if we take in our hands the *Commentary on Virgil's Aeneid*, written by fourth-century scholar Servius Marius Honoratus, the author makes reference to «Albunea. [...] quia est in Tiburtinis altissimis montibus»: in late antiquity, the Tiburtine Sibyl is seen by Romans as an oracle set amid «very high mountains».

Are such mountains the Apennines themselves? Not all sources provide a confirmation of that, but some of them appear to support the idea of a Tiburtine Sibyl residing among the cliffs belonging to the Apennine chain.

Let's take the famous 'legend of the nine suns', a prophecy that was attributed, in early-Christian times, exactly to the Tiburtine Sibyl. As we already detailed in our previous article *World of the Sibyl: the Italian Apennines and the Sibillini Mountain Range*, this legendary tale concerns a visionary dream made by a hundred Roman senators at the same time, a vision that the Sibyl explained as a succession of historical ages from the Roman empire to the advent of Christianity, future wars and finally the end of the world. This legendary account was copied in dozens of manuscripts across Europe.

In some of the manuscripts reporting the prophecy of the Tiburtine oracle on the nine suns (for instance, the Düsseldorf Codex C.1, as reported by German scholar Ernst Sackur), the Sibyl tells the senators that she will provide them with a response «in apenninum», on the Apennine mountains, considered as a sacred and unblemished place as opposed to corrupted Rome. This same indication is present in *Le Livre de Sibille (The Book of the Sibyl)*, a thirteen-century anglo-norman work attributed to Philippe de Thaon, which reports the same Tiburtine Sibyl's episode by saying that the senators should move «ki apenin anun».

Fig. 17 - The excerpt on the Tiburtine Sibyl and the legend of the nine suns from the *Livre de Sibyle* (Bibliothèque Nationale of France, Département des Manuscrits, Français 25407)

In the *Liber Mirabilis*, a sixteenth-century book containing a collection of prophecies, the Tiburtine Sibyl invites the Roman senators «in monte apennin».

Fig. 18 - The legend of the nine suns in the *Liber Mirabilis*, 1525

Finally, a 1563 printed edition of the works written by Bede the Venerable, a benedictine monk who lived in the eighth century in England, reports the words «ad Apenninum montem».

Fig. 19 - The legend of the nine suns as it appears in the second book of the *Operum Venerabilis Bedae presbyteri*, published in Basel in 1563

Even though all the listed quotes pertain to centuries which are much later than Roman age, it is clear that some link existed between the Tiburtine Sibyl and the Apennines, as the connection is repeatedly stated throughout hundreds of years, and certainly was not considered as unfounded - especially if we keep in mind the location where the town of Tibur is set, on the first elevations of the Apennines which are encountered eastward of Rome.

So, if we have to trace any Sibils in the Apennines, sure enough one eligible candidate is the Tiburtine Sibyl, with her shrine set in in Tibur, or modern Tivoli, lying by the Tiburtine Mountains, rugged elevations set in a picturesque environment featuring waterfalls and precipitous cliffs. And sometimes referred to, in ancient sources, as the Apennines.

Once more, we cannot retrieve any specific reference to our much-sought Apennine Sibyl, in the area lying between the Italian provinces of Umbria and Marche. For the time being, we are still blocked with our current result: according to the outcome of our short ride across Roman literature, no

specific mention of an Apennine Sibyl which would have resided in the vicinity of Norcia has ever been written by any known author belonging to the literary milieu of ancient Rome.

So, at this stage of our search, we are still stuck to the fifteenth century as the age of the earliest mention of a Sibyl active as an oracular center in the territory of Norcia, as detailed in the literary works written by Andrea da Barberino and Antoine de la Sale.

Where should we turn now? Let's look for other clues in ancient geography. Perhaps we will be able to find some reference there. Let's go and search.

7. A close scrutiny of the Tabula Peutingeriana

A major problem in the study of the legend of the Apennine Sibyl is that no mention of it appears to be available before the fifteenth century. Medieval sources do not offer any relevant quote, nor Roman literature provides further clues on that specific Sibyl, despite a wealth of mentions about a number of other Sibyls that can be found in the literary tradition of ancient Rome.

However, literature is not the only heritage that ancient Rome has bequeathed to us. We will now turn to one of the most amazing relics that the Roman civilization has ever handed down to our present world. It is a unique token coming straight into our hands from Imperial Rome, something that is so bewildering as to be considered a sort of miraculous legacy that has crossed the millennia almost untouched to witness the vastness and magnificence of the Roman Empire.

This extraordinary witness is the Tabula Peutingeriana.

The Tabula Peutingeriana is a long roll of parchment, originally 22 feet long and now divided into 11 sheets, preserved at the Österreichischen Nationalbibliothek, the Austrian National Library in Wien, as the Codex Vindobonensis no. 324.

Fig. 20 - A full-length image of the Tabula Peutingeriana (Codex Vindobonensis no. 324), preserved at the Österreichischen Nationalbibliothek in Wien

If you put the parchment sheets one after another and side by side, the entire Roman Empire suddenly appears before your very eyes. From the British Islands to the left, to the farthest borders of the world known in antiquity to the right, beyond the Caspian Sea, India and the island of Sri Lanka, it shines in splendour in front of your amazed gaze.

The Tabula Peutingeriana is a cartographic map of the Empire of Rome, with its towns, imperial roads, geographical features and main sites of interest. It was copied from some lost original by an unknown monk possibly at the dominican abbey in Colmar, in today's north-eastern France, during the thirteenth century; but scholars believe that the fundamental source of the map is to be ultimately ascribed to the large first-century B.C. map drawn by Marcus Vipsanum Agrippa, the great consul, general and architect who served under Emperor Octavianus Augustus. Agrippa's map was completed in the early first century A.D., sculpted on marble and mounted on a public building in Rome.

The Tabula Peutingeriana is an incredible geographical diagram which comes to us with information that consistently seems to belong to the first century A.D., with a number of further updates added in later centuries. For instance, the imperial capital city of Constantinople is shown, a town that was only founded in 330 A.D.; however, other geographical indications pertain to much earlier times, with a major release possibly having been drawn in the third century A.D.

The map reappeared in history at the beginning of the sixteenth century thank to the work of two German scholars, Konrad Celtes and Konrad Peutinger, after whom the chart was named.

The map is very detailed, though not drawn with the intent to comply with the rules of any kind of modern geographical projections: roads, rivers, coastlines and towns are meticulously depicted, with indications of distances, of great importance in the view of a military use of the diagram.

Can we find, in the Tabula Peutingeriana, any indication of a site in the Italian Apennines dedicated to an oracle or a Sibyl?

Let's look from a closer distance to the region of the map which portrays what we call today the Sibillini Mountain Range. In the territory labelled as «Picenum», the map shows the Apennine fastnesses as a brown winding line which runs through the whole of Italy, as a veritable spine. In the area of the Sibillini Mountains, we see the Via Salaria drawn as a thin red line, going through Reate (today's Rieti) and then approaching the mounts at Phalacrinae (the birthplace of an Emperor, Vespasian).

Fig. 21 - The central portion of the Italian peninsula as it is depicted in the Tabula Peutingeriana, with Rome on the right side

Fig. 22 - The territory between the province of Picenum and the river Tiber in the Tabula Peutingeriana

Subsequently, from the lost outpost of 'Ad Martis', possibly referring to a settlement set near a shrine dedicated to Mars, the ancient road reaches 'Surpicano', in the vicinity of today's Arquata del Tronto, and then 'Ad Aquas' - recognised as modern Acquasanta Terme - until it ends up in Ascoli Piceno.

Fig. 23 - The area of today's Sibillini Mountain Range in the Tabula Peutingeriana

In the map, no reference is made to any oracular site set in the vicinity, or on a nearby mountain.

Is this a reliable evidence of the fact that Romans knew nothing about an Apennine Sibyl? Not really, even though it is assured that the Table contains no positive confirmation of the fact that they did actually know.

In fact, many places are actually missing on the Tabula Peutingeriana: for instance, it reports the name of the nearby town of Spoletium, but no reference is made to Norcia, well known by the Latins as 'Nursia'. The Table was designed to provide information on the highways and roads crossing the Roman Empire, being outside the scope of the map to detail each and all settlements or worship places scattered across the vast territory subject to the rule of Rome. As to Sibyl-relevant sites, we find mentions of Tibur (today's Tivoli) and Cumae, with its Lake of Avernus, but no trace of Delphi in Greece.

So, we find no evidence, in the Tabula Peutingeriana, of any oracular site in the Apennine region set between Phalacrinae and Spoletium. This is no ultimate proof as to the non-existence of such a site, because the Tabula omits a large number of places which in antiquity were actually there.

However, one thing is sure: the Tabula does not provide any positive confirmation that an Apennine Sibyl was active in this portion of the Roman Empire. Again, we are not able to find any reference to such a Sibyl in ancient sources.

Again, we are stuck in a situation in which no mention of an Apennine Sibyl is available before the fifteenth century.

And yet, we can still resort to a final resource, one that should not fail: Claudius Ptolemy, the renowned Greco-Roman geographer, who lived in the second century of the Christian Era.

Why Ptolemy? Because, according to many authors, he did mention the Apennine Sibyl in his ancient treatise, "Geography", in which he described the whole world known in antiquity.

Can it be the ultimate evidence we are strenuously looking for? Did the Apennine Sibyl really appear, for the first time in history, in the work of an author who lived one hundred years after Jesus Christ was born?

That would be the 'smoking gun' we have been seeking so eagerly, the proof of a classical ascendancy of the Sibyl whose abode lies in the vicinity of the town of Norcia, in Italy.

Are we finally on the right track? Let's see in the next paragraph whether we are on a fair course, or not.

8. Ptolemy and the Sibyl

We are still in search of a clue which may provide us with a confirmation that, in antiquity, the Apennine ridge in the vicinity of Norcia, in Italy, was known as the abode of a Sibyl. At the current stage of our search, no such clue was found. No literary reference to an Apennine Sibyl pertaining to an age earlier than the fifteenth century was retrievable, either in the Middle Ages or Roman times.

However, we have still a last card to play: ancient geography.

We saw that the Peutingerian Table, a sort of fossil of geographic cognition at the time of imperial Rome, provides to us no practical hint. But what about Claudius Ptolemy, one of the greatest geographers of ancient times?

In fact, an astounding, most interesting clue suddenly seems to appear in the work written by Feliciano Patrizi-Forti, a nineteenth-century local historian from Norcia, and in a book by Father Fortunato Ciucci, a seventeenth-century monk who was likewise born in Norcia: the two of them report a very same quote, with minor differences, that they both maintain they took from Claudius Ptolemy, the most prominent astronomer, astrologer and geographer of the early Roman Empire.

And, amazingly enough, Ptolemy's quote seems to provide a straight reference to the Sibyl's cave and the lake of Norcia. In the words reported

by Patrizi-Forti in his *Historical Chronicles of Norcia (Memorie Storiche di Norcia)*, Book III, Chapter XXII (Fig. 1):

«The said Mount Vettore [...] has on its top a lake and a cavern renowned in antiquity. In fact Ptolemy wrote as follows in his eighth Table: “Norcia, the town set amid the peaks of the Apennines, near the mount known as Vettore”; he also adds: “the Lake of Norcia, whose waters raise with a perennial motion, and then in turn they are seen fall down, not without the utter astonishment by the onlookers; there evil demons reside, and common people believe that they provide answers when summoned. [...] And furthermore in the Apennines there is a huge and frightful cavern which people calls the Sibyl's cave, about which many tales are told, according to which many sorcerers were once frequently seen by the cavern, so much so that the inhabitants of Norcia were forced to seal that Sibyl's cave”».

Fig. 24 - The excerpt allegedly taken from Claudius Ptolemy's *Geography* as mentioned in Feliciano Patrizi-Forti's *Memorie Storiche di Norcia*

[In the text by Patrizi-Forti: «Il monte Vettore anzidetto [...] ha sulla sua vetta un lago ed un antro famosi presso gli antichi. Difatti Tolomeo nell'ottava Tavola scrisse: “Nursia civitas inter montes in jugo Appennini montis, qui dicitur Victor”; ed aggiunge: “Lacus Nursinus, cujus aquae

perpetuis motibus surgere, vicissimque subsidere cernuntur non sine magna admiratione, unde ibi Cacodaemones choabitare, vocatosque responsa dare vulgus putat. [...] Est etiam in Appennino immane horribileque antrum quod Sybillae caverna vulgo dicitur, de qua multa recitantur, quamobrem cum nursini frequenter olim Magorum numerum ad hunc locum concurrere conspexissent, specum Sybillinum operire conati sunt”»].

Patrizi-Forti's quote echoes a similar mention reported by Father Fortunato Ciucci: «Of those Ptolemy spoke and wrote: “amid the peaks of the Apennines, near the mount called Vettore, there is a Lake of the Demons, whose waters raise...”».

[In the text by Fortunato Ciucci: «Di questi parlando Tolomeo così lasciò scritto: "in jugo quoque Appennini Montis, qui Mons Victor vocatur est Lacus Demonum, cujus Aquae perpetuis Montibus salire, vicissimque subsidere cernuntur, non sine magna admiratione, unde ibi cacodemones inhabitare, vocatosque responsa dare imperitus, vulgus putat. [...] Di questa [Grotta della Sibilla] ne parla anco Tolomeo dicendo: "Est etiam in Apennino immane Antrum quod Sibillae Caverna vulgo dicitur, de qua multa fabulosa, ac imposteribus recitantur"»].

The two almost identical quotes - if they were true - would represent the ultimate confirmation of the fact that the Apennine Sibyl, together with its nearby lake, was definitely known by ancient Romans: Claudius Ptolemaeus, a most illustrious mathematician, astronomer and geographer in antiquity, who lived in Alexandria in the second century A.D., did write, in actual truth, amazing words about the Sibyl's cave set in the vicinity of the ancient town of Norcia.

Unfortunately, this is not true at all.

In his original work *Geographike*, written in Greek by the great geographer, no reference to an Apennine Sibyl is present. So where did Patrizi-Forti and Ciucci draw their peculiar excerpts from?

The answer is contained in a seventeenth-century edition of Ptolemy's *Geography* compiled by Antonio Giovanni Magini, an Italian scientist and geographer, in year 1617.

Fig. 25 - Antonio Giovanni Magini's edition of Ptolemy's *Geography* published in Arnhem in 1617

The book is not a mere translation of Claudius Ptolemaeus' work into Latin: in the first chapter, as Magini himself states, he intends to publish «an annotated commentary to the first book on Geography written by Ptolemy» («in primum librum Geographiae Claudii Ptolemaei commentaria et annotationes»), together with the original list of antique geographical sites reported by Ptolemy. In the second book, Magini provides «not only Ptolemy's geographical maps but also most recent ones, which show the face of the whole Earth as it is known in our age» («continens praeter Ptol. recentiores etiam Tabulas, quae Universae terrae faciem nostro aeo cognitam exhibent»).

Because the title of Magini's book is «Geographiae, tum veteris, tum novae» («Geography, both antique and new»). He himself tells the readers that «I add plenty of explications of the said geographical tables, with reference to each single portion of the globe, Empires, Kingdoms, Duchies and any other Realms, as they are found in our own age» (in the original

Latin text: «addite sunt copiosissime ipsarum tabularum explicationes, quibus singula Orbis partes, Imperia, Regna, Ducatus, aliaque Dominia, prout nostro tempore se habent»).

And it is in the second, modern part of Magini's book that the Apennine Sibyl is mentioned. In the map of the «Marcha Anconae once known as Picenum», part of the collection of new, modern maps published by Magini, we find a tiny indication in the upper portion of the print: «Monte de la Sibila» («Mount Sibyl»), it reads.

Fig. 26 - The map of the Italian province of Marches as it appears in Antonio Giovanni Magini's *Geography*, with the position of the Sibyl's cave indicated

And if we go to the subsequent chapters, providing a description of the whole earth «according to what we know in our more recent age» («secundum recentiore[m] nostri temporis rationem»), in the chapter which describes Italy and the region of Ancona we find exactly the same wording reported by both Patrizi-Forti and Ciucci, with minor changes only.

Fig. 27 - The excerpt on the Lake of Norcia and the Sibyl's cave in Antonio Giovanni Magini's *Geography*

The Sibyl, the cave, Norcia, and the lake. But those are not Ptolemy's words. The great geographer, who lived in the second century A.D., never wrote a single word about all that. Instead, that text was written by Giovanni Antonio Magini at the beginning of the seventeenth century.

So, again, we have no real mention about an Apennine Sibyl which may come up from antiquity. Ancient Romans simply seem to know nothing about her.

We are stuck, again and again, to the impossible task of retrieving a mention of the Apennine Sibyl that is older than the ones provided by Andrea da Barberino and Antoine de la Sale in the fifteenth century.

And now, at this stage of our search, it seems we have ended up in a blind alley. As a matter of fact, it appears that something might sound wrong to our ears about the legend and lore concerning the Apennine Sibyl.

Can we get out from this dead end? And - if so - how could we do that?

Let's try to sum up all the data we have been able to retrieve up to now, and to pinpoint the strange condition into which we have finally ended up. And

- perhaps - we might succeed in starting up again from this very same blind alley.

Maybe, we might begin to head off towards the right direction.

9. The impenetrable mist from which the Sibyl came

At the end of our journey back into the past, across the Middle Ages and the centuries of ancient Rome, we are now ready to summarise the results of our search for early literary mentions of the presence of an Apennine Sibyl in the mountainous ridges set between the Italian provinces of Umbria and Marche.

Did we find any hint of her presence? No. We only found an echoing void, an impenetrable mist from which the Apennine Sibyl appears to have come out, as a shining, lonely star, at the beginning of the fifteenth century, starting her successful travel into the subsequent ages.

We know pretty well that a Sibyl was described as living in the remote area lying between Norcia and Montemonaco by two fifteenth-century authors: Andrea da Barberino, who mentioned the Sibyl in his romance *Guerrino the Wretch*, and Antoine de la Sale, who depicted a visit to the cave of the «Royne Sibile» (Queen Sibyl) in his *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl*.

However, if we go further back in time, we find absolutely nothing. We get lost in the whirling, apparently unfathomable fog of history.

Nothing is reported about the presence of a Sibyl in the late Middle Ages, when a French monk and abbot, Petrus Berchorius, mentioned the sinister renown of a magical Lake of Norcia (today's Lakes of Pilatus, set just a few miles from the Sibyl's cave) in his *Reductorium Morale*, and a poet from Tuscany, Fazio degli Uberti, wrote a few verses on a gloomy mount and lake of Pilatus. We are in the fourteenth century and they both mention no Sibyl. And no Sibyl is mentioned, either, in the *Charters of the Municipality and People of the Land of Norcia (Statuti del Comune et Populo della Terra di Norcia)*, a collection of laws and rules dating to the same century.

Fig. 28 - An artist's impression of the Sibyl emerging from the mists of time at the beginning of the fifteenth century (composite image by the author)

If we push ourselves further back, we jump straight (owing to the lack of any other relevant references) to the fourth century, with Lucius Caecilius Firmianus Lactantius and his *De divinis institutionibus adversus gentes*, in which the Latin author enumerates a list of ten Sibyls, considered by scholars as a classical standard catalogue: however, only three are the Sibyls connected to Italy (the Cumaean, the Cimmerian and the Tiburtine). And we saw that no one of them features any relation to the Sibillini Mountain Range.

Only the Tiburtine Sibyl seems to present a specific link to the Italian Apennines, with references to the existence of such a link being contained in many ancient manuscripts and subsequent printed editions of the 'legend of the nine suns'; however, we saw that that link is to be interpreted as a

mere connection to the picturesque, precipitous mountains on which Tibur (today's Tivoli, near Rome) is set, part of the larger Apennine range.

We can retrieve further mentions about some kind of oracular site lying amid the Apennines, as reported by fourth-century *Historia Augusta*, with reference to Emperor Claudius II Gothicus, and by *The Twelve Caesars*, a work written by first-century Latin writer Gaius Suetonius Tranquillus, in the passages dedicated to Aulus Vitellius Germanicus Augustus. However, today no one can tell where such site or sites might have been set, as the listed classical authors say nothing about their exact location. And they mention no Sibyl, either.

Even the Tabula Peutingeriana, which comes to us from the times when the Roman Empire was a ruling power, makes available no information on a possible sibilline site in the region set between the ancient provinces of Picenum and the river Tiber. The specific area in the Tabula where the Sibillini Mountain Range raises its peaks appears to be empty.

Finally, if we had placed our hope in the 'smoking gun' provided by Claudius Ptolemy, the great second-century Roman-Greek geographer, who allegedly had reported about the Sibyl, her cave and the nearby lake in his renowned *Geographike*, we ended up with a totally disappointing result: that utterly remarkable mention was not taken from Ptolemy, instead it was drawn from a commented edition published by Antonio Giovanni Magini, an Italian scholar and geographer, in year 1617.

That's all. The Apennine Sibyl, who suddenly popped up during the fifteenth century in the works by Andrea da Barberino and Antoine de la Sale, seems to have originated almost from nothing, as a sailing ship emerging all of a sudden from the thick mists which enshroud the sea, with all its masts and yards and rigs shining with bright, ominous light.

So the question is: where does this Apennine Sibyl come truly from?

Has that Sibyl really journeyed a long way across the centuries and through that inscrutable fog, after having started her travel in ancient times and having remained unseen until she emerged in the fifteenth century? Or, was she the more recent product of some strange condensation of that thick,

whirling mist, in which her myth took form not in antiquity, but just very close to the beginning of the fifteenth century?

A dire dilemma now appears to erupt before our very eyes: what if the legend and lore about an Apennine Sibyl weren't that ancient? What if that Sibyl established her mythical presence in the Sibillini Mountain Range not much before Andrea da Barberino and Antoine de la Sale wrote their books?

What if no Sibyl had never been there?

Notwithstanding that, there is no doubt that down there, amid the precipitous peaks of the Sibillini Mountain Range, some kind of tradition, some kind of lore was already present: a cavern was there, and a lake, and some queer, sinister renown of that remote places, as attested by Petrus Berchorius and Fazio degli Uberti a century before Andrea da Barberino and Antoine de la Sale. Gloomy, magical places, which are deeply nested into the Italian Sibillini Mountain Range.

So if a Sibyl was never there, what was there instead?

We conclude this astounding travel into long-gone centuries in search of the Apennine Sibyl with a number of thrilling questions. Questions that have never been posed in such ominous, blood-curdling terms ever before.

Yet our investigation goes on. And we will see, in a future series of articles, what answers we might be able to find. The long journey of the Apennine Sibyl across the centuries continues to unfold all its charming fascination.

We will try to probe that fog: the dense, eddying fog from where a Sibyl emerged. And we will see whether those mists are really inscrutable, or not.

Michele Sanvico